

RESEARCH REPORT

**The Impact of the COVID-19
Pandemic on Transgender
Communities in Indonesia
(2020 Survey)**

FOREWORD FROM THE AUTHORS

*Edison Butar Butar
& Nova Christina*

IT is true that the COVID-19 pandemic affects everyone and causes unexpected crises, from economic crises to health to a sense of security for everyone. For transgender groups, this crisis is nothing new. Transgender groups in Indonesia have experienced a crisis from childhood to adulthood. Since then until today. This crisis occurs in the private sphere to the public domain. Starting from the stigma, persecution to criminalization experienced by transgender groups has put them in a crisis situation before the COVID-19 pandemic strikes the world in early 2020. The presence of the COVID-19 pandemic for transgender people in Indonesia is like alcohol spills on open wounds, or like wounds which is present right next to the old wound that never dries. It is here to increase the pain, until finally the transgender group is increasingly put in a condition that is experiencing multiple crises.

These new wounds are what the Indonesian Transgender Coalition is trying to dig deeper into through us. Page after page of the results of this research is provided to its readers to see more about the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on transgender groups in Indonesia. It is possible that among some readers, when reading the results of this study, found that there are some conditions that have been commonly found in transgender people. We will not argue with it, because it is true. Because as we have said before

that the COVID-19 pandemic is only exacerbating what has been bad before. However, we believe that something worse that hundreds of people experience is something that we still need to understand and immediately recover from. One way to recover is to identify more deeply the location and shape of the new wound. That is what we are presenting in this study.

The results of this research will not reach the readers without the hands and thoughts of the people involved. We would like to thank the Indonesian Transgender Coalition (JTID) especially Rebecca Nyuei and the other 14 Steering Committees who trusted us both to carry out this research. Thank you very much, which we also cannot forget to say to the 14 enumerators, all of whom are transgender friends who have contributed a lot in the data collection process of this research. You all are amazing!

The last thing we want to say is that a study is inseparable from limitations and challenges. Therefore, we are very open and also happy if there are parties who wish to make improvements to the results of this research in the future or use the results of this research for the needs of advocacy for transgender rights in Indonesia through other spaces. These good intentions will ultimately answer our dreams for a world and Indonesia that are friendly and equal to transgender groups.

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CONTENTS

01

Introduction

Research Background— 2

Purpose and Research Scope — 5

02

Methodology

Key Questions — 7

Sampling & Data Collection — 8

Data Analysis — 9

Research Challenges & Limitation — 10

03

Research Findings

Respondent Profile — 12

Access to Information

(Lack of Access to Information Increases the Risk of Contracting COVID-19) — 17

Economic Impact

(Reduce Income, Desperate to Work with the Risk of Contracting COVID-19) — 21

Impact of Independence

(Going Home Means Getting Hurt, Staying Means Being Ignored) — 29

Security

(A Sense of Security that is Getting Further Away in Crisis Situations) — 36

Health Impact

(Enduring in Limitation) — 40

04

Conclusion & Recommendation

Conclusion — 48

Recommendation — 50

a

Researchers Profile

Nova Christina — 53

Edison Butarbutar— 54

b

Attachment

Questionnaire— 56

01

INTRODUCTION

RESEARCH BACKGROUND

BY the end of December 2019, a new virus outbreak was known as the COVID-19 virus (Corona Virus Disease 2019) which is a member of the other Corona Virus family, namely the SARS virus (severe acute respiratory syndrome) 2002-2003 in southern China and the MERS virus (Middle East respiratory syndrome) in the Middle East, especially Saudi Arabia in 2012. The SARS corona virus was reported to have spread to at least 26 countries in Asia, Europe, North America and South America. Meanwhile, the MERS corona virus is spread in 27 countries in Asia, Africa, Europe and America. Even though it has stopped, MERS cases are still occurring, until now there have been reported as many as 2,494 MERS positive cases with 858 deaths.¹

Even though it is still in the same Corona family (Corona), COVID-19 has a significant difference from MERS and SARS. If the previous two viruses can only transmit when the condition is severe, the COVID-19 virus can transmit three (3) days after being infected. This causes the transmission rate of COVID-19 to be quite high. According to data from worldmeters.info, in a period of 6 months from December 2019-May 2020, the COVID-19 virus has spread to 215 countries in the world, starting from Asia, Africa, Europe, America,

Australia and even countries in Oceania². This means that this virus has spread to almost all parts of the world. Therefore, the World Health Organization or WHO declared this virus a global pandemic³. By referring to worldmeters.info, there were 4,198,418 cases with a total of 284,102 deaths and 1,500,685 declared healthy⁴.

It must be admitted that COVID-19 has an impact on all aspects of people's lives globally. As stated by Central Bank of Indonesia, globally some of the best-developed countries in the G20 are making efforts to increase awareness of global economic risks. Therefore, it is necessary to implement effective policies in monetary, fiscal and structural terms.

Indonesia is one of the countries affected by COVID-19, and even ranks the second highest in Southeast Asia with the number of cases as of May 11, 2020 is 14,265, recovered 2,881 and died 991⁵. Although it is second in Southeast Asia, Indonesia until 11 May 2020 still found 18 new cases, while Singapore had no new cases recorded until that date. This shows that handling COVID-19 in Indonesia is still a challenging duty for the government, especially in ensuring the rate of

¹ <https://bebas.kompas.id/baca/opini/2020/04/08/sejarah-panjang-virus-korona/>
² <https://www.worldometers.info/coronavirus/#countries>

³ <https://www.merdeka.com/jateng/sejarah-perkembangan-virus-corona-dari-masa-ke-masa-kln.html>
⁴ *ibid*
⁵ <https://COVID19.go.id/>

decline in cases, the availability of health infrastructure and also economic infrastructure⁶.

The policies related to COVID-19 carried out by the government are still ineffective. Both policies in reducing the level of transmission even in ensuring the availability of social and policies related to economic support to all levels of society. For example, the implementation of Large-Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB) as well as Working at Home which is not evenly distributed throughout the provinces has caused new cases to appear. In addition, the implementation of the PSBB has also caused many polemics and new problems, for example, economic support for the community is considered not reaching all levels of society. Especially the LGBTI groups in Indonesia.

In discussing about LGBTI groups and their relationship to COVID-19, based on the results of qualitative research conducted by OutRight International, namely the impact of COVID-19 on LGBTI⁷ conducted through in-depth interviews with 59 LGBTIQ people in 38 countries, there were 7 impacts felt by LGBTI groups, namely:

1. Loss of livelihoods that leads to the increase food vulnerability
2. Limited access to health facility
3. Increased risk of domestic violence
4. Increased anxiety
5. Increasing social stigma
6. Abuse of state power
7. Fear about the continuity of the organization including funding support

Unfortunately, the aforementioned research above did not involve Indonesia, the informants from Southeast Asia only involved the ones from Singapore. Whereas we understand, the context of Indonesia is very different from other countries in Southeast Asia such as Singapore. Differences in geo-political countries, social, cultural, and

economic levels are variables that will contribute to these differences and variants of impact. For example, in the situation of the COVID-19 pandemic, the Government of Indonesia used the opportunity for the COVID-19 pandemic to ratify several draft policies that criminalize LGBTI. For example, the revision of penal code (RKUHP), Omnibus Law and the Family Resilience Bill⁸. Geopolitical conditions like this are not taken into account in the research above.

In addition, Indonesia is a country with a high level of persecution against LGBTI. For example, Arus Peladata in 2013⁹ and 2017¹⁰ (in 2013, there were 89% of LGBTI individuals experiencing violence and in 2017 it was 92%). The results of these two studies indicate that violence against LGBTI people still occurs. In fact, although it did not appear to have increased significantly, there was still an increase of 3.13% over the past four years. Violence received by LGBTI individuals can be classified into five types of violence, namely psychological, physical, economic, cultural and sexual¹¹.

Apart from the violence experienced by LGBTI groups in general, transgender individuals have the highest rate of discrimination¹². Discrimination against transgender groups who are considered to be higher is due to the impact of their physical expression (gender expression) which is often considered not in accordance with their gender, and this is not in accordance with the views of society in general¹³.

Another study that supports the data above was conducted by Arus Pelangi 2013 which showed that transgender people were the group that had the most victims of violence, namely 35%. Transgender individuals with less formal education have fewer choices in their field of work. Many of them then work as sex workers,

⁶ <https://tirto.id/telat-tangani-corona-COVID-19-pemerintahan-jokowi-bisa-digugat-eG8y>

⁷ https://outrightinternational.org/sites/default/files/COVIDsReportDesign_FINAL_LR_0.pdf

⁸ <https://www.pikiran-rakyat.com/nasional/pr-01360473/di-tengah-pandemi-corona-pemerintah-dan-dpr-dinilai-tak-punya-niat-baik-terhadap-rakyat>

⁹ Menguak stigma, 2013 (<https://aruspelangi.org/perpustakaan/>)

¹⁰ Research Documentation and Monitoring Report; Situation of Human Rights and Access to Justice for LGBTI

Community in Indonesia, 2017 (<https://aruspelangi.org/perpustakaan/>)

¹¹ LGBT Exclusion in Indonesia and its Economic Effect, 2017, hal. 17

¹² Koeswinarno. 2004. Hidup sebagai waria [Living as a transgender person]. (LKis, Yogyakarta, Indonesia).

¹³ Indonesian NGO Coalition on LGBTI Issues. 2012. Alternative report of Indonesia's ICCPR State report 2013. December 2012. Available at: http://tbinternet.ohchr.org/Treaties/CCPR/Shared%20Documents/IDN/INT_CCPR_NGO_IDN_14708_E.pdf.

street singers, living with a double stigma, as transwomen and as sex workers¹⁴. Transgender individuals, on average, do not have Indonesian Identity Cards (KTP), making their position more vulnerable to harassment from state officials, as what often happens is that they are grouped into groups that are considered to disturb security and order, such as homeless people, street singers and sex workers¹⁵.

The conditions above, are the conditions before the outbreak of COVID-19 in Indonesia. This means that there are new impacts faced by LGBTI groups, especially transgender people in Indonesia. According to the results of a rapid survey conducted by Sanggar Swara in March 2020 regarding the impact of COVID-19 on transwomen in several areas in Jakarta, Banten and West Java (Jabodetabek), it was found that there were 600 transwoman individuals who could not work and could not support their daily needs due to the implementation of physical distancing¹⁶. In addition, another survey, namely the impact of COVID-19 on the LBQ women and transman groups, with 42 respondents from 12 provinces, showed that 37.8% of LBQ and transmen had no access to food supply, 35.6% of them cannot pay rented rent, 20% cannot pay for

electricity and 6.7% cannot continue the business¹⁷.

The research above shows that there is an impact of COVID-19 on LGBTI people. However, until now there has been no research looking at the particular impact of COVID-19 on transgender individuals in Indonesia. Both studies above are limited to regional limitations and non-Trans gender identity limitations. In fact, as we know, transgender groups have a higher level of vulnerability and are different from lesbian, gay and bisexual groups. This is in line with what was conveyed in Arus Pelangi's research above. In Indonesia, region is a variable that influences the level of vulnerability to transgender people.

Based on the above description, this research focuses on the Impact of COVID-19 on transgender groups in Indonesia. In particular, how the COVID-19 pandemic affects the quality of life for transgender people in Indonesia. From the news in various mass media, we all know how the COVID-19 pandemic has affected the world, especially in the economic sector. Meanwhile, it is also known how far LGBTI groups in Indonesia, including transgender groups, have experienced various forms of discrimination and violence. Thus, the data from this study is important to be used as a reference in developing further support for transgender groups in Indonesia.

¹⁴ Adhi, S.; Irawan et al. n.d. Iktibar jurnalisme warga bagi komunitas waria di Yogyakarta [Examples of citizen journalism for the transgender community in Yogyakarta]. Available at: <http://perpus.org/doc/jT-iktibar-jurnalisme-warga-bagi-komunitas-.html>.

¹⁵ Pride at Work: A study on discrimination at work on the basis of sexual orientation and gender identity in Indonesia, Hal. 14

¹⁶ Rapid assessment CRM, 2020

¹⁷ https://www.instagram.com/p/B_-QOkznOrl/?igshid=qh2qnqjl80bm

PURPOSE AND RESEARCH SCOPE

THE purpose of this research is to see the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on transgender people in Indonesia. This research is focused on transgender, due to the consideration of the different and quite high levels of vulnerability from other identity and orientation groups.

The scope of this research includes Indonesia with sample and population calculations which will be explained in the methodology section.

Three impacts will be examined in the research, namely; (1) Fulfillment and Protection of Law (security), (2) Welfare, (3) Independence. These three impacts originate from 3 strategic issues of the Indonesian Transgender Network (JTID).

02

METHODOLOGY

KEY QUESTIONS

Key questions are developed based on the 3 impacts that will be examined in the research. The key questions can be seen in the following table:

Security	1. How the COVID-19 pandemic affects the safety of transgender people on a daily basis?
Welfare	2. How the COVID-19 pandemic affects transgender groups in carrying out economic activities? 3. How the COVID-19 pandemic affects the quality of life for transgender people, especially in the economic aspect?
Independence	4. How the COVID-19 pandemic affects the independence of transgender people?

Based on the 4 key questions above, a questionnaire was developed with structured questions both closed and open ones and asked to respondents who are transgender groups from various backgrounds (geographic, economic, social and gender identity/SOGIESC).

The questionnaire developed records information related to the following aspects:

1. Respondent profile
2. Access to information related to the COVID-19 pandemic
3. Impact on income/economy aspects
4. Impact on independence aspects
5. Impact on security aspects
6. Impact on health aspects

SAMPLING AND DATA COLLECTION

THE data was collected using a survey method with a quantitative approach. Due to the absence of a sampling frame in the form of individual transgender data in each province in Indonesia, a non-probability sampling technique, which is a combination of purposive and quota sampling techniques, was carried out, by selecting sampling locations based on logical and practical considerations. Determining the reasons for choosing the sampling location and respondent is realized as an important factor in this sampling model.

As for the determination of sampling, the first process was carried out by dividing into three regional zones, namely western, central and eastern Indonesia. Referring to developments during sampling preparation (30 May 2020), the three zones defined above were categorized based on the status of the COVID-19 case to then determine the selected provinces, namely the red, yellow and green zones.

For western Indonesia it is categorized as a red zone, with the selected provinces being North

Sumatra, DKI Jakarta, West Java and East Java. Central Indonesia was concluded as the representative of the yellow zone with the selected provinces being Bali, Central Kalimantan, South Kalimantan and South Sulawesi. Finally, eastern Indonesia is categorized as a region that represents a green zone, with three selected provinces Maluku, Papua and West Papua.

The target total sample to be collected is 450 respondents. Then in determining the sample, the quota total target sample is divided by 3 (representing 3 zones). So that for each zone a target of 150 respondents was set.

In determining the proportion between the number of transwoman and transman respondents, it is done by referring to the average number of transwomen and transmen participants in the implementation of activities. It is agreed afterward that the ratio between transmen and transwomen is 1: 3. From the calculation results, the targets per province are as follows:

Total sample: 450

- Red zone: 150/4 provinces = 38 respondents/province → Transmen: 10, Transwomen: 28
- Yellow zone: 150/4 provinces= 38 respondents/province → Transmen: 10, Transwomen: 28
- Green zone: 150/3 provinces= 50 respondents/province → Transmen: 17, Transwomen: 33
- The sampling determination also takes into account the balance between young transgender groups (aged 18-35 years and adults (36 years and over).

In the next process, per province is targeted to have 2 enumerators to be responsible for conducting interviews. The selected enumerators are part of the transgender community which consists of one transwoman and one transman. Based on the targeted quota respondents per province and per gender identity, enumerators were asked to identify and prepare data on potential respondents.

Data collection was done on a paperless basis, by using the mobile data collection software/application (Kobo) which was carried out by using smartphone. This data collection process can minimize the non-sampling error aspect, especially in the form of enumerator

errors in following the flow of questions in the questionnaire. In addition, from an environmental aspect, data collection techniques with mobile data collection will also reduce paper usage so that it is more friendly to environmental conservation or balance. The data collection process was carried out from 17-30 June 2020.

The survey briefing process was conducted online to 19 enumerators. As part of the preparation for data collection, a questionnaire testing process was also carried out. Each enumerator was asked to interview two people. The results of the questionnaire test (pre test) provide input for the improvement of the questionnaire and other technical aspects of data collection.

DATA ANALYSIS

Data analysis was carried out using SPSS to see trends in general and per variable on the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on transgender groups in Indonesia. In the analysis process, it was also observed how specific trends (per independent and dependent variable) such as the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic according to gender identity, age, social and economic background and region. With cross analysis, it is possible to be more specific in observing the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on transgender groups in Indonesia.

In testing the correlation between two variables, the analysis process is carried out with a non-parametric testing procedure. This test is carried out because of the belief that the distribution of the data collected is not a normal distribution. This is mainly because the sampling method used is non-probability sampling. Spearman's correlation analysis was carried out in the analysis process to see the strength, direction and significance of the correlation between two variables.

RESEARCH CHALLENGES AND LIMITATION

BY conducting a pre-test before data collection is actually carried out, it is recognized that it is very helpful to minimize technical problems in remote data collection. From the target of 450 respondents, the total number of respondent data collected in the process was 438 respondents. However, it was still acknowledged by the enumerators, even though they had gone through the pre-test process — especially in the early stages — it still took time to master the questions on the questionnaire. The most common obstacle was related to information on the monthly income of the respondents. Enumerators found that there were respondents who objected to conveying the true value of income, especially for respondents who were estimated to have high incomes. To overcome this, the supervision team consisting of the two main researchers monitors the incoming data on the online data collection server every day.

The biggest obstacle was found in West Papua, especially for data collection on trans male respondents. One of the enumerators, until the end of data collection, had not shown any

progress at all. Similar case was also found in South Kalimantan. In the end, the interview process for South Kalimantan and West Papua was conducted with the help of enumerators from other provinces.

The interview process was originally designed to be carried out entirely by telephone, considering that this survey was carried out during the COVID-19 pandemic and PSBB is still in effect in several provinces in Indonesia. However, the enumerator team later admitted that they experienced technical problems in conducting telephone interviews and then decided to conduct face-to-face interviews. The COVID-19 infection prevention protocol was established as a standard procedure that must be followed during face to face interviews.

One of the positive aspects of choosing a transgender group as part of the enumerator team is the opportunity to know the condition of fellow transgender friends, especially in other areas. The data collection process was also used by enumerators to strengthen networks between cities/districts in each province.

03

RESEARCH
FINDINGS

RESPONDENT PROFILE

This research is focused on looking at the impact of COVID-19 on transgender people in Indonesia. The definition of transgender refers to the SOGIESC Arus Pelangi basic education module¹⁸. Transgender respondents in this study were divided into 2 categories of gender identity, transwomen and transmen. The total number of respondents surveyed was 438 respondents consisting of 323 transwoman respondents (74%) and 115 transman respondents (26%). The ratio of 3: 1 on the number of respondents was previously consulted with JTID, which is based on two things. First, this comparison follows the composition of the Steering Committee (SC) representation on the internal JTID. Second, there are challenges in finding or identifying transman respondents. Because the issue of transman is a very new issue, especially in provinces outside Java, so many groups of transmen not knowing the difference between transmen and lesbian masculine.

Graphic 1. Comparison of the number of respondents per gender identity

¹⁸ Transgender is the Individual who identify themselves differently from their birth assigned gender and/ or sex.

Based on the numbers above, the respondents were subsequently categorized by age. This is important to do to see the impact of COVID-19 based on age. The age division categorized in this study is youth with a range of 18-35 years and adults with a range of 36+. Of the 438 respondents, the number of respondents with a young age was 263 (60%) respondents and adult age 175 (40%) respondents. The comparison of respondents based on age with this figure is considered sufficient to represent the involvement of transgender groups from young and adult ages. The relationship between age and gender identity shows that the number of young transwomen is 174 (54%) and adult transwomen is 149 (46%). Meanwhile, young transmen were 89 (77%) respondents and adults 26 (23%) respondents.

Graphic 2. Composition of respondents by age

Respondents in this survey were spread across 11 provinces. The distribution area above is divided into 3 areas, namely the red zone (West Indonesia) which includes the provinces of North Sumatra, DKI Jakarta, West Java and East Java. The yellow zone (Central Indonesia) includes the provinces of South Kalimantan, Central Kalimantan, Bali and South Sulawesi) and the green zone (East Indonesia) includes the provinces of Papua, West Papua and Maluku. The number of respondents in each province in the red and yellow areas was 38 respondents while in the green zone the number of respondents was Papua 41 respondents, West Papua 43 respondents and Maluku 50 respondents. Initially the number of respondents in the green zone was planned for 50 respondents per province with a composition of 33 transwoman respondents and 17 transman respondents. This composition follows the 3: 1 ratio predetermined at the start of the sample calculation planning. However, in the process of identifying respondents, there were 2 provinces in the green zone, namely Papua and West Papua which could not fulfill the quota for the number of transmen respondents. In Papua Province there were only 8 transman respondents and West Papua Province only 10 respondents.

Graphic 3. Distribution of Respondents

Graphic 4. Distribution of respondents' areas based on gender identity

The profile of the distribution of respondents in each province based on age shows that there are three provinces with the composition of the number of young people and adults at the same rate, namely 50%: 50%, namely North Sumatra, South Sulawesi and Central Kalimantan. As many as 6 provinces with a ratio of youth greater than adult are in Maluku (86%: 14%), West Papua (79%: 21%), Bali (71%: 29%), South Kalimantan (66%: 34%), Papua (59%: 41%) and West Java (55%: 45%). The remaining two provinces show that the number of young respondents is lower than adults, namely East Java (39%: 61%) and DKI Jakarta (45%: 55%).

Graphic 5. Distribution of respondents by age

Based on regional zones, the comparison of the age of the respondents based on the Graphic below shows that in the red zone there are 47% young and 53% adults. In the yellow zone, there are 59% young and 41% adults. Whereas in the green zone there are 75% young and 25% adults.

Graphic 6. Age distribution of respondents based on regional zones

Apart from the distribution of regions and also age, the last variable seen from the respondents' profiles is the level of education of the respondents. Of the 438 respondents, 434 respondents answered education level. From that number, it shows that more than half (57%) of transgender people in Indonesia only graduated from high school / equivalent. This figure is higher than the education level of the Indonesian workforce in 2019, which was 29.94%. The same is true for diploma and university level (undergraduate and above bachelor degree). As many as 14% of the transgender group received education at the diploma and undergraduate level, with a difference of 1.24% higher than the level of Indonesian education in 2019, which was 12.76%.

Graphic 7. Respondents education level

There were several significant differences in the level of education between the transwomen and the transmen. The most significant difference is that only less than 1% of transmen have only graduated from elementary school, while the transwomen are quite high at almost 10%. This difference is about 9%. In addition, at the university level of education (diploma, undergraduate and above S1) only 10% of transwomen attended this level, while among transmen group there was 27%. From this data it can be concluded that the education level of transmen is higher than transwomen. This condition cannot be separated from the fact in the patriarchal community that the transwomen group as a group that is

considered descended or inferior because of their femininity is more prone to experiencing bullying than the transman group. In addition, many of the transwoman groups have had to leave or have been expelled from their families at school age and then go to other cities to survive by working as sex workers, musician and salon workers. This causes many transwoman groups are unable to complete their education.

Graphic 8. Comparison of education levels of transmen and transwomen

ACCESS TO INFORMATION

Lack of Access to Information Increases the Risk of Contracting COVID-19

Since January 2020, information related to the COVID-19 pandemic has continued to increase and have been milling about in the media. The Indonesian government has even created a special information portal regarding the development of the COVID-19 case via <https://covid19.go.id/>. However, in this study it is important to see whether this information is known by transgender groups in Indonesia. There are two aspects to look at regarding access to information, namely the intensity of following the news on the development of COVID-19 in Indonesia and the information media used to follow the development of COVID-19.

The survey results show that more than half are transgender intensively follow the development of COVID-19, which is 59%. Even so, the rest (41%) showed that the intensity of following the development of COVID-19 information was very low. There are even transgender people who have never followed COVID-19 (3%). This figure is quite alarming because almost half of transgender people in Indonesia have very little information on the development of COVID-19 news. Even though changes in the flow of information on COVID-19 are changing very quickly, this is because the COVID-19 pandemic is a new virus in which the Indonesian government is still looking for methods to prevent this virus. The lack of information related to COVID-19 will have an impact on the lack of knowledge of the dangers of spreading COVID-19 and how to avoid the spread of the COVID-19 virus, thereby increasing the high risk of contracting the COVID-19 virus.

Graphic 9. The intensity in following the development of COVID-19 information

The comparison of the intensity following the development of COVID-19 information between transwomen and transmen is also very different. In general, the transwomen group had a higher intensity, namely 20% of transwomen very often followed the development of COVID-19 information, while among transmen only 9%. This is because the development of information related to COVID-19 is very relevant to the work of the transwoman group, the majority of which are sex and salon workers (see discussion in the chapter on the impact on economic conditions).

Graphic 10. Comparison of the intensity of accessing COVID-19 information between transwomen and transmen

The intensity of following the development of COVID-19 at young and adult ages shows almost the same percentages, namely 41% and 43%. Whereas for transgender adults (36+) the most significant figure, namely 45%, often follows the development of COVID-19. When added together between often and very often, young transgender people are at 54% who are intensely following the development of COVID-19, while adult transgender people are 68%. This 14% difference shows that transgender adults are more intensely following the development of COVID-19 than young transgender groups.

Graphic 11. Comparison of the intensity of accessing COVID-19 information by age

The second aspect related to access to COVID-19 information that was surveyed was the information media accessed in following the development of COVID-19 information. There are 3 information media most used by respondents in accessing information related to COVID-19, namely social media (YouTube, FB, IG, Twitter) at 29%, followed by news on television at 25% and news / online media at 17%. Using social media and online media as a means of information sources is a fairly common condition in today's era. Even so, it takes analytical skills to sort out valid information with information with a hoax tendency. Especially in the context of COVID-19 information, hoax information is quite high, so the Indonesian government even has to create a special team to ward off hoaxes related to COVID-19 on the official portal related to Indonesian COVID-19 (<https://covid19.go.id/p/hoax-buster>).

The interesting aspect from the survey results related to access to information, only 14% of transgender groups got information about COVID-19 from government socialization and 2% information from medical personnel. This figure is quite low, so there is potential that transgender information in Indonesia regarding COVID-19 is information that does not come from the government, which means it is very likely that the information is also a hoax.

Graphic 12. Source of information on the development of COVID-19

The comparison of the sources of information used by transwomen and transmen in accessing developments in COVID-19 information is generally not much different. Only a few sources of information showed a significant difference, namely the transwoman group had a higher percentage who used word of mouth which is 21% compared to transmen 13%. The 21% figure in the transwoman group can be concluded that during the COVID-19 pandemic, the transwoman group interacted more with other people than the transman group.

Graphic 13. Comparison of the use of sources of information on COVID-19 between transwomen and transmen

ECONOMIC IMPACT

*Reduce Income, Desperate to Work
with the Risk of Contracting COVID-19*

THE first question asked to respondents regarding income is whether they had a regular source of income before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. What is meant by a steady source of income is a source of income that is received routinely and is sufficient for monthly needs. From a total of 438 respondents, almost all respondents (95%) stated that they have a regular source of income before COVID-19 pandemic occurred. When the COVID-19 pandemic occurred, the percentage of respondents who stated that they had a permanent source of income decreased. From the previous 95% of respondents, during the COVID-19 pandemic only 70% stated that they still had a steady source of income.

The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the transgender community can also be seen in the decline in average monthly income. Before the pandemic, the average monthly income was around IDR 4 million (IDR 4,308,425). The data shows that only about 32% of respondents stated that they had an income below the rupiahs. Although not in a prominent number, most respondents (37%) stated that they had an income of two to five million rupiahs. Then, there are 25% of respondents who stated that they had an income in the range of five to ten million rupiahs. The rest, about 6% of respondents stated that they had income above ten million rupiahs.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the average income received decreased by 58% to around one point eight million rupiahs (IDR 1,802,968). From the income category data, it can also be seen that the majority of respondents stated that they had an income of below two million rupiahs per month. This was followed by the next category, namely the income ranges of between two and five million rupiahs as stated by 29% of respondents. Then, only about 5% of respondents stated that they had income above five million rupiahs.

Graphic 14. Comparison of Income Before and During the COVID-19 Pandemic (in IDR)

■ Before Pandemic
■ After Pandemic

When compared between transmen and transwomen, the composition of income as described above is not different. Both transmen and transwomen, the majority had income below two million rupiahs during the COVID-19 pandemic, followed by the percentage of respondents who stated that they had an income of between two and five million rupiahs. In the transwoman group, before the pandemic, at least 37% of respondents stated that they had an income of two to five million rupiahs, followed by 30% of respondents stated that they had an average monthly income of below two million rupiahs. In the transman group, before the pandemic at least 38% of respondents stated that they had an income of under two million rupiahs. While the other 37% have an average monthly income of two to five million rupiahs.

For income above 5 million rupiahs, the data shows that before the pandemic there were 27% of respondents who stated that they had an income of five million to ten million rupiahs. Meanwhile, only 17% of trans men stated that they had an income of more than five to ten million rupiahs per month. For income above ten million rupiahs, the two groups showed almost the same percentage (6% for transwomen and 7% for transmen).

During the COVID-19 pandemic, both transwomen and transmen mostly stated that their income had decreased. In the transwoman group, from 30% of respondents who stated that they had an income of less than two million rupiahs, it increased by 124% to 67% of

respondents. In addition, for the transman group, the increase in the number of respondents who stated that they had an income of less than two million rupiahs increased by 63%, from previously 38% to 63% of respondents.

For income of five to ten million rupiahs, both transwomen and transmen experienced a decrease of about 85%. In the transwoman group, from 27% of respondents who stated that they had an income of more than five million to ten million rupiahs, it decreased to 4% of respondents. Meanwhile, in the transman group, from 17% of respondents it decreased to 3% of respondents.

The difference is seen in the proportion of respondents who have a monthly income of more than ten million rupiahs. For the transwoman group respondents, only 1% of respondents stated that they had an income of more than ten million rupiahs. Meanwhile, in the transman group, at least 4% of respondents had an income of more than ten million rupiahs per month during the COVID-19 pandemic. Although the numbers in both groups decreased, the biggest change occurred in the transwoman group. In the transwoman group, the decline occurred up to 85%. Where before the pandemic 6% of transwoman respondents stated that they had an income of more than ten million rupiahs, it decreased drastically to 1%. For the transman group, the decrease that occurred was smaller than that of the transwomen, which was around 39% (from 7% to 4%).

Graphic 15. Comparison of Income (in IDR) by Gender Identity

Regarding the source of income, in the research it was realized that transgender individuals generally have more than one source of income. The main source of income is still in the informal sector. Only about 17% of respondents stated that they work in the formal sector, whether they work in private companies, government and non-government institutions. The majority, about 83% of respondents work in the informal sector. During the COVID-19 pandemic, there was something interesting about the percentage of respondents who worked in the formal sector. Although it did not change significantly, there was an increase in the percentage of respondents who rely on formal sector sources of income to 19%. During the pandemic, there has been an increasing interest in working for companies and non-governmental organizations.

As a source of income, working in salons/spas/reflexology and as sex workers were still a mainstay both before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. Prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, data showed 33% of respondents worked in salon/spa/reflexology and 7% offered mobile salon/makeup/massage services. At least 27% of respondents stated that they work as sex workers.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, around 28% of respondents said they still relied on working in salon/spa/ reflexology as a source of income and 7% offered mobile salon/makeup/massage services. For respondents who stated that they

were still sex workers there were 28%. During the COVID-19 pandemic everyone is required to avoid close physical contact, work in salon/ spa/reflexology and rely on income as sex workers are still a mainstay in the transgender community.

When analyse separately, between the transwomen and transmen, there are differences in sources of income. In the transwoman group, both before and during the COVID-19 pandemic, almost half of respondents relied on their income from working in a salon (45% before the pandemic and 36% during the pandemic). Almost the same as the proportion of working in a salon, more than a third of transwoman respondents stated that they rely on earning income as sex workers (37% before the pandemic and 36% during the pandemic). Two sources of income that were also disclosed as a source of income for the transwoman group were mobile salon/makeup/massage services (9% before the pandemic and 8% during the pandemic) and also being entrepreneurs (especially salon/makeup/wedding entrepreneurs) with the percentage before and during the pandemic by 10%. Even though they admit that they have experienced a decrease in income during the COVID-19 pandemic, it seems that there are no options for the transwoman group to earn income. Economic activities that rely on physical contact (salon, make-up, massage as well as sex workers) are still carried out to fulfill their daily needs.

In the transman group, almost one third of respondents rely on their income by working in the formal sector, especially in private companies. Before the pandemic, at least 27% of respondents stated that they worked for private companies, and during the pandemic there was a slight increase in respondents who relied on working in private companies (30%). Trading is also stated as a source of income, before the pandemic 20% of transmen respondents claimed this and it also increased to 25% during the pandemic. One source of income that transman respondents stated to be quite reliable was working in the transportation service sector, both offline and online. The respective percentages were 10% before the pandemic and increased during the pandemic to 14%. This type of work also includes jobs that are at risk of contracting COVID-19 because they are still physically close to customers.

Graphic 17. Comparison of 6 Main Sources of Income of Transmen Before and During the COVID-19 Pandemic

In the transman group, around 14% of respondents who previously relied on earning income from working in the entertainment industry, especially in cafes and karaoke, experienced a decline due to the closure during the COVID-19 pandemic. During the pandemic, only about 4% of transmen respondents stated that they still worked in cafes or karaoke. Although less than one tenth of the total transman, survey data also show an increase in the number of respondents who rely on finances from family support. During the COVID-19 pandemic, at least 7% of respondents stated family support as a source of income. This percentage has increased by 60%, from the previous only about 5% who stated family support as a source of income.

One of the factors that may affect the occupation or source of income between two transgender groups is the level of education. For both transwomen and transmen, the majority of the latest education levels are senior high school level. The difference is seen in the proportion of education levels below and above senior high level. In the transwoman group, after senior high level, the last level of education that was in second place as mostly mentioned is junior high school level (26%), followed by elementary school education (10%).

Meanwhile, in the transman group, after the senior high level, the bachelor level was in second place, which respondents mentioned as the last education level (20%). The level of education equivalent to junior high school is in third place with a percentage of 9%. Furthermore, the level of education equivalent to a diploma was stated by 6% of male transman respondents as the last education level.

By comparing the data for the two groups, it can be seen that for the transwoman group, the level of education ranges from elementary to senior high school. Meanwhile, for the transman group, the level of education ranges from junior high school to undergraduate/bachelor (S1). It is logical that with a lower educational level compared to the transman group, the opportunity for the transwomen to rely on the formal work sector as a source of income is getting smaller.

Graphic 18. Respondents Education Level by Gender Identity

To see the strength and direction of the correlation between the two nominal and ordinal variables, a non-parametric correlation test was performed using Rank-Spearman correlation analysis. The variables tested were education level and income level. This correlation test is carried out with the following objectives:

1. To see the level of strength of the relationship between two variables
2. To see the direction (type) of the relationship between variables
3. To see the significance level of the relationship between the two variables being tested

From the output of the Rank-Spearman correlation analysis, to see the level of strength of the relationship between the variables of education level and income level, a coefficient of 0.125 (before the COVID-19 pandemic) and 0.088 (during the COVID-19 pandemic) was obtained, indicating a weak correlation level. From the direction of the relationship between the two variables, although weak, there is a positive relationship between education level and income level both before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. For the level of significance of the correlation, for the level of education and income level before COVID-19, there is a significant relationship between the two variables, namely 0.009 (<0.05). However, not with the relationship between education level and income level during the COVID-19 pandemic, the significance value of 0.067 is greater than 0.05. Therefore, it can be concluded that in this survey of transgender groups, the level of education did not really have a big influence on the level of education. There are other factors that also affect it.

Table 1. Analysis of the Spearman Correlation between Education Level and Income

			Education Level	Income before pandemic	Education Level	Income during pandemic
Spearman's rho	Education Level	Correlation Coefficient	1	.125(**)	1	0.088
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	0.009	.	0.067
		N	434	434	434	434
	Income	Correlation Coefficient	.125(**)	1	0.088	1
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.009	.	0.067	.
		N	434	438	434	438

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Regarding the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on meeting daily needs, even though income has seen an impact in the form of a decrease in income, most respondents admit that they are still able to meet their daily needs. During the survey, they were asked whether the respondent was able to meet several basic needs during the pandemic: food, shelter, electricity, clean water, medical treatment and communication. Except for the need for medication if sick, generally respondents admitted that they could still meet basic needs.

Graphic 19. Ability to Meet Basic Needs During the COVID-19 Pandemic

However, the problem is, to meet this need, more than two-thirds of respondents (69%) stated that they are making other efforts (apart from relying on the income they earn) to fulfill their basic needs. Of the 304 respondents who stated that they had made other efforts, almost half (47%) relied on loans from family/relatives. The second option taken is to sell assets that are owned (38%). Meanwhile, around 11% of respondents were forced to pawn their assets to survive the COVID-19 pandemic. What is worrying is that there are 11% of respondents who stated that they then do jobs that are very risky for the transmission of COVID-19. About 8% of respondents stated that they had to become sex workers during the pandemic, and 3% offered mobile salon/make-up/massage services.

Graphic 20. Other Efforts to Survive During COVID-19 Pandemic

From observations of assets owned before and during the pandemic, there was a decrease in the percentage of respondents. Both before and during the COVID-19 pandemic, smartphones, motorbikes, savings/money deposits, television are four types of assets that are generally owned by transgender groups. When compared to the percentage before and during the pandemic, it can be seen that a decrease in the number of respondents regarding asset ownership. For gold/other jewelry, from 17% of respondents who claimed to have owned it before the pandemic, it decreased to 10%. For motorbikes, from 59% of respondents who claimed to own a motorbike before the pandemic, it decreased to 56%. Then the decrease for savings/money savings was from 52% to 28%, there was a decrease in ownership by 47%. Thus, it can be seen that up to the time data collection was carried out, generally the fulfillment of needs was carried out by using existing savings.

Table 2. Comparison of Asset Ownership Before and During the COVID-19 Pandemic

Type of Asset	Before pandemic	During pandemic
House	12%	12%
Land	3%	3%
Store/kiosk	1%	1%
Motorcycle	59%	56%
Car	5%	4%
Gold/jewelry	17%	10%
Savings/money	52%	28%
Computer/laptop	11%	9%
Smartphone	94%	93%
Television	51%	50%
Bicycle	0%	1%
Camera	1%	1%
Refrigerator	7%	6%
Salon equipment and tools	4%	4%
Electric fan	3%	3%
AC	2%	2%
Washing machine	1%	1%
Stocks and bonds	0%	0%
Other	5%	4%
Total	328%	288%

Meanwhile, when asked whether the respondent has dependents economically? More than half (52%) stated that they had two dependents on average. With all the impacts that transgender groups have felt, most respondents stated that they could last a maximum of 3 months. Among them, 57% of respondents stated that they were only able to survive for the next month, and 35% stated that they were able to survive for more than a month to the next three months from the time the data was collected.

Graphic 21. Respondents with Economic Dependents

Graphic 22. Estimated No of Months Surviving during Pandemic

IMPACT OF INDEPENDENCE

*Going Home Means Getting Hurt,
Staying Means Being Ignored*

This section will highlight how COVID-19 impacts the independence of transgender groups in Indonesia. The variables seen are related living space and access to support during the COVID-19 pandemic. During the last six (6) months, especially before the COVID-19 pandemic, it shows that 74% of transgender groups in Indonesia live independently either in boarding rooms (43%) or in rented/owned houses (31%), only 18% are still living with family. This makes sense, given the fact that many transgender groups leave or are evicted from their homes when their families find out their identities.

In a pandemic situation, not having an independent or permanent place to live is a very distressing condition. This will have the potential to increase vulnerability to contracting the COVID-19 virus. The survey results show that as many as 8% of the transgender group do not have independent housing. Thus, they have to live at work, stay at a friend's/relative's house, some even move around or not having permanent place to stay. This figure also shows that prior to the COVID-19 pandemic there were still transgender groups who did not have a proper place to live and even could not afford to have their own residential house either rented or owned.

Graphic 23. Living place of the respondents for the last 6 months

Based on gender identity, it shows that the transman group lives with their family more than the transwoman group. Although the difference is only 5%, this figure indicates that more of the transwoman group leaves their home or family sooner than transman group. Since it cannot be denied, the transwoman group has higher visibility than the transman group. This data also proves that so far, many cases show that the transwoman group at a young age have left and been evicted from their homes or villages because of their gender identity as transwoman.

Graphic 24. Living place per gender identity

During the COVID-19 pandemic, many people who had migrated or lived independently wanted to return to their family homes, especially those in big cities with various factors, some because they were fired unilaterally, could not work to meet basic needs or because they really wanted to celebrate the day Eid with family. When asked whether there was an intention to return to their family home during the pandemic, more than half (75%) of the transgender group who did not live with their family (362 respondents) stated that they had no desire to return to their family home. This condition shows two things, first, the fear of the release of the COVID-19 virus to families such as the government's appeal, but the most specific thing related to the situation of transgender groups is because many transgender groups have indeed been kicked out of their families, forcing them to stay alone and independent. Even in the COVID-19 pandemic situation.

Returning to the family home for most transgender people will add new problems and increase the hurt and experiences of violence they have experienced. This fear is mostly experienced by the transwoman group. The survey results showed 76% of the transwomen stated of having no plan to go home while the transmen were at 73%. Both percentages still show that both transwomen and transmen feel that going home is not what they want, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic. Although they have to endure sufficiently caring conditions and struggle to fulfill the basic needs during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Graphic 25. The level of intention to return back to the family during the COVID-19 pandemic

The COVID-19 pandemic that has an impact on meeting basic needs is felt by many people, including transgender groups. As mentioned in the section on economic impacts, transgender groups in Indonesia experienced a 60% decrease in income during the pandemic. Therefore, the need for assistance to meet basic needs is very much needed.

More than half of transgender groups in Indonesia (71%) have received support from other parties during the COVID-19 pandemic. Although 71% of transgender groups had received support during the COVID-19 pandemic, there is a very significant difference between transwomen and transmen.

Graphic 26. Comparison of assistance received by gender identity

At least 81% of the transwoman group stated that they had received support. This figure is quite high compared to the transman group, where only less than half (44%) stated that they had received assistance. This condition occurs because the majority of the transwomen work as sex workers and salons, which in fact during the COVID-19 pandemic they could not work and earn income. This has resulted in

the focus of support in the early days of COVID-19 being aimed at the transwoman group. For example, the Crisis Response Mechanism (CRM) consortium, which since March 2020 has distributed support for the impact of COVID-19, initially only focused on the transwoman group. As the result, it is quite natural that more transwomen receive assistance than transmen.

By province, out of 312 transgender respondents who had received support. The transgender people who received the least amount of support came from South Kalimantan 4% and Maluku 6%. Meanwhile, the provinces that received the most support were West Java and East Java (12%), followed by North Sumatra (11%), DKI Jakarta and Central Kalimantan 10%.

Graphic 27. Support Recipients by Province

The survey results show that the parties that provide the most support to transgender groups are NGOs. The NGOs referred to here are the majority of NGOs working on LGBTI issues. This means that if the collective figures for trans/LGBTI and NGOs are added up, as much as 78% of transgender groups in Indonesia get support from fellow LGBTI organizations. If we return to the provinces of South Kalimantan and Maluku, which have the lowest percentage of receiving support, this is because in these provinces the number of organizations NGOs that have a good perspective on transgender groups is very limited. Apart from that, most of the fundraising carried out by NGOs are concentrated in big provinces such as DKI Jakarta, West Java, East Java and North Sumatra.

The government only contributes 27% to provide support to transgender groups in Indonesia. This figure shows the low level of government initiative and support in providing support to transgender groups during the COVID-19 pandemic. In fact, the initiative was born from LGBTI organizations/NGOs and other NGOs as well as fellow trans/LGBTI collectives. In fact, when compared between government and non-government (civil) institutions, the figures show that the government contributed only 27% of the

respondents while non-governmental organizations (fellow civil society) were received by 110%¹⁹ respondents. From this significant comparison, it can be concluded that the government's commitment to ensuring the fulfillment of the basic rights and basic needs of transgender people during a pandemic is quite low.

Graphic 28. Support Provider

The following is data on the distribution of assistance to transgender people during the COVID-19 pandemic by province.

Table 3. Support Sources by Province

	Unknown people	Religious Institution	NGO	Government	Work place	Friends	Collective trans/LGBTI	Political Party	Other
DKI Jakarta	6%	25%	72%	47%	0%	9%	0%	0%	3%
West Java	0%	6%	83%	8%	0%	8%	6%	0%	3%
East Java	29%	34%	100%	8%	0%	3%	0%	34%	0%
North Sumatra	0%	0%	97%	24%	0%	3%	0%	0%	0%
South Kalimantan	0%	0%	18%	82%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Bali	7%	0%	90%	0%	3%	35%	0%	0%	3%
South Sulawesi	0%	0%	92%	8%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Central Kalimantan	0%	0%	72%	41%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Papua	0%	0%	28%	66%	7%	7%	55%	3%	0%
West Papua	59%	0%	14%	24%	0%	3%	31%	0%	0%
Maluku	5%	0%	42%	32%	5%	16%	0%	0%	0%

¹⁹ The percentage amount is more than 100% because each respondent can respond to more than one response/choice (multiple responses)

Some things that can be drawn from the table above are:

1. Bali provincial government never provide support to transgender groups during the COVID-19 pandemic. In fact, the ones that provide the most support are NGOs, at least stated by 90% respondents.
2. South Kalimantan and Papua are the 2 highest provinces that receive support from the government, namely 82% and 66%, meaning that more than half of the transgender respondent group in these two provinces have received support from the government.
3. Of the 11 provinces, only 3 provinces where transgender groups claim to have received assistance from religious institutions to transgender groups and all are in the Java island region (DKI Jakarta, East Java and West Java).
4. Of the 9 provinces above that will hold regional head elections (*Pemilukada*) simultaneously in 2020, there are 2 provinces whose political parties provide support to transgender people, namely East Java (34%) and Papua (3%). This is interesting, especially in the East Java region, where there are indications that transgender groups are asked to collaborate to raise votes for the 2020 regional election.
5. The three highest provinces that received support from NGOs were East Java (100%), North Sumatra (97%) and South Sulawesi (92%).

Although almost a third of respondents stated that they had experienced difficulties in accessing support (26%), the majority (74%) stated that they did not experience any challenges in accessing support. The percentage of transgender respondents who stated that they did not experience this difficulty did look high because it was like the data previously mentioned that at least 78% of respondents received support from LGBTI NGOs and also collectives among trans/LGBTI people, so it is quite natural that they will not experience this. trouble. In fact, the interesting thing from this data is that the percentage of 26% who stated that they have experienced difficulties is important for further analysis.

Graphic 29. Experience in Accessing Support during Pandemic COVID-19

The highest figure shows the reason why transgender groups have difficulty accessing support is because the amount of support is limited (24%). Limited amount of support is a common condition in Indonesia, but the question then is, why when support is limited, transgender people cannot get it? The answer is in the second and third order of the data below. Whereas in terms of providing assistance, transgender groups experience rejection because of the stigma and sentiment towards their gender identity as transgender (21%). Because of this stigma, they were not prioritized for support (19%). Apart from not being a priority, a fairly common reason is that they do not have identity card (12%).

Graphic 30. Difficulties in Accessing Support during Pandemic COVID-19

The case of not having identity card (KTP) in the context of transgender groups in Indonesia is different from that of the general population. It should be further seen that transgender groups do not have KTP/KK because many of them were evicted and left their family homes because of their gender identity as transgender. So, it is not just an administrative problem when transgender groups do not have a KTP. There are experiences of violence that cause conditions to occur. If seen from the data above, that the transgender group is placed as a group that is not a priority in accessing assistance because of gender identity and restrictions on access to KTP for them is at 42%. This figure is not surprising, since from various studies related to transgender and LGBTI, the fulfillment of access to justice and basic rights is still very low. However, in this study, this figure is very concerning because the condition of the COVID-19 pandemic has taken away the spaces for their independent economic fulfillment. In addition, they also do not get support in fulfilling basic rights just because of their gender identity and are considered as unprioritized.

The form of support received by transgender groups during the COVID-19 pandemic shows that groceries have the largest percentage (97%) received by transgender groups in Indonesia, followed by cash by 26%.

Graphic 31. Form of Support Received

SECURITY

A Sense of Security that is Getting Further Away in Crisis Situations

THE survey results showed that transgender groups in Indonesia experienced several acts of violence and security incidents during the COVID-19 pandemic. As many as 19% of transgender groups stated that they had experienced security incidents and discriminatory treatment during the COVID-19 pandemic. The security incidents they experienced are as follows, as shown in the diagram below:

Graphic 32. Forms of violence experienced during the COVID-19 pandemic

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the highest number of cases involving security forces was 41%. These security incidents consisted of threats by security forces (36%) and being arrested by security forces (5%). When digging deeper, several reasons for these threats and arrests were made because several transgender groups left their homes to continue working during the COVID-19 pandemic. The decision to leave the house during a pandemic to keep working is an option that many transgender groups must

continue to make because the government does not provide them with basic necessities, as mentioned in the subsection related to support.

The inability to meet basic needs because they have to follow the government's social restriction policies, which the government also does not ensure the fulfillment of basic rights causes 3% of transgender people in Indonesia to also be expelled from rented/boarding houses. Violence from society is also quite high for transgender people during the pandemic. Such as being threatened by residents (21%), threatened by thugs (21%), evicted from their homes (4%) and acts of violence and robbery by 21%. That is, if this figure is added up, 66% of transgender groups experienced violence from society during the COVID-19 pandemic. In addition, although the rate of violence being evicted from their homes only shows a small number, if we look further it means that as many as 4% of transgender people in Indonesia must leave their homes in the COVID-19 pandemic situation, which this condition will also increase. vulnerability to catch the COVID-19 virus.

The data above shows that the COVID-19 pandemic situation is precisely proportional to the increase in violence against transgender groups in Indonesia. The interesting thing from the data above is that during the pandemic, the number violence committed by fellow citizens or the community was higher than in cases where the perpetrators were security forces.

Regarding access to justice, this survey also tries to see whether the cases experienced by the transgender group above are reported or not to the police. The results showed 91% of transgender people did not report the experienced cases. This figure is quite alarming, meaning that almost all of the cases they experienced during the COVID-19 pandemic just evaporated without any legal treatment.

When explored further, what were the reasons they did not report these cases. The following are the respondents' answers which are contained in the diagram below:

Graphic 33. The Main Reasons Did Not Report the Violence Cases Experienced

As many as 21% of transgender groups did not report cases of violence because they felt fear. The fear that often occurs is the existence of stigma and acts of revictimization by the police when they want to report cases. This fear is also closely related to other data, namely that the perpetrators of violence are security forces (4%) so that transgender groups feel that there is no benefit (2%) and will add new violence from the apparatus.

Another reason is that 14% of transgender people think that the violence they experience is still tolerable. This attitude is a form of normalization of violence experienced by transgender groups who think that they deserve violence because of their gender identity. This normalization of violence is understood both personally and collectively. Because of this attitude, transgender people do not feel the need to increase the problem (18%). Many transgender groups feel that reporting a case of violence that they have experienced will increase or increase the problem.

Normalization of violence above is also very closely related to the capacity and procedures for reporting which are still lacking in the transgender group (18%), not only capacity issues, the problem of reporting experiences who have received discriminatory treatment and revictimization makes them reluctant and lazy to report the cases they experience.

As many as 21% of the transgender group considered not reporting because they admitted guilt and violated the rules. There are two conditions that can be seen from this figure. First, because they have too often normalized the violence they have experienced so far, many transgender groups have finally admitted guilt or violated the law. For example, when they sing on the street or become street sex workers. They consider that being buskers and sex workers is a mistake against the law, so when they are arrested, they consider it to be in accordance with legal procedures. Second, even if they were arrested or experienced violence for violating social restrictions during COVID-19, the choice to leave the house to work is the only option they have because they have to meet their basic needs. Because according to the data mentioned regarding support, only 20% of transgender people get support from the government and from other parties, they cannot access it because it is not a priority and there are acts of discrimination because of their identity. Thus, even though the reason for breaking the rules is quite high at 21%, this figure should be seen as a form of the multiple layers of violence they experienced before.

When trying to see the relationship between cases of violence on the grounds of not reporting. The main reason that arises from cases of violence being evicted from their place of residence is that they are afraid to report the case (50%) and do not understand how to report it (50%). This condition shows that there is an unequal power relationship between boarding house owners and transgender groups, especially with their very visible identities and expressions. On the other hand, this fear is also due to the low capacity of transgender people in conducting non-litigation advocacy such as mediation and negotiation in civil cases.

Another situation occurred in cases of being threatened and arrested by the authorities, the main reason expressed by respondents for not reporting their cases was fear (75%). Fear of the security apparatus is a condition that causes further access to justice for transgender groups in Indonesia. Usually this fear is because security forces often revictimize transgender groups when they report their cases. This fear also has the potential for legal impunity for officials who commit violence against transgender groups. Lots of cases of violence committed by law enforcement officials have evaporated because of the issue of impunity. Violence cases that are often normalized or considered by transgender people are threats of people (34%), threats of thugs (36%), acts of violence (66%) and theft of money (100%).

Table 4. Relationship Between Cases of Violence and Reasons for Not Reporting Cases

	Fear	The perpetrators of violence were security forces	Don't know how to report	Don't want to escalate the problem	Can still be tolerated	Admitting wrong/breaking the rules	The problem has been resolved	Not sure there is any benefit
Threatened by people	8%	8%	0%	17%	17%	33%	17%	0%
Threatened by the security forces	42%	11%	16%	0%	0%	32%	0%	0%
Threatened by thugs	36%	0%	27%	9%	27%	0%	0%	0%
Evicted from residence	50%	0%	50%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Arrested by security/order officials	33%	33%	0%	0%	0%	33%	0%	0%
Threats from unknown people	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	100%	0%
Threat of robbery	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	100%	0%
Money theft	0%	0%	0%	100%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Violent action	0%	0%	33%	33%	33%	0%	0%	0%
Other	0%	0%	25%	0%	25%	25%	0%	25%

The last part of the impact on security, through this survey, tries to measure the sense of security felt by transgender groups before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. The comparison of the diagram below shows that there has been a significant change in the sense of security of transgender people in Indonesia before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. Before the pandemic 3% of transgender people felt insecure and this figure increased dramatically to 55%, meaning that at the time of the COVID-19 pandemic, more than half of transgender people in Indonesia felt insecure. There was an increase of 1,733% before and during the pandemic related to the insecurity felt by transgender people in Indonesia. In addition, the majority of transgender groups in Indonesia (64%) feel safe, but during the pandemic, this figure experienced a drastic reduction to 12 percent. This means that there is a decrease of 81% related to the feeling of security. It is also interesting, related to the status of very insecure, where before the pandemic the transgender group did not experience it while in the pandemic it increased to 13%.

Graphic 34. Transgender safety status before and during the COVID-19 pandemic

The figures above are proven by the increase in violence against transgender people during the COVID-19 pandemic as previously mentioned. Therefore, in the conditions of the COVID-19 pandemic, access to a sense of security for transgender people is even farther away, which before the pandemic also felt insecure.

HEALTH IMPACTS

Enduring in Limitation

In order to see the impact on health conditions in transgender groups in Indonesia, efforts are made to look at three aspects, including: hormone therapy, mental health and access to ARVs. Among transgender people, hormone therapy is common. During the COVID-19 pandemic, we want to see if there are significant changes in access to and consumption of hormones. With the existence of activity restrictions and constraints related to financial conditions, it is assumed that it will be an obstacle for transgender groups to access hormone therapy.

Regarding mental health, the COVID-19 pandemic will certainly put its own pressure on anyone's mental condition, not only on the transgender group. However, as part of a community group that is vulnerable to acts of discrimination and violence, this survey wants to look specifically at how the pandemic affects the mental condition of transgender groups. Especially by emphasizing the pattern in dealing with any challenges and pressures that arise.

The last health aspect that will be observed in this survey is the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on access to ARVs. It is generally known that the transwoman group has been identified as one of the groups at high risk of being infected with the HIV virus. Moreover, in discussing findings related to the impact on economic conditions, most of the transwomen still rely on earning income as sex workers (37% before the pandemic and 36% during the pandemic).

When respondents were asked whether before and during the COVID-19 pandemic did hormone therapy, most said they did not. The data below shows that before the pandemic, at least 66% of transgender respondents stated that they did not take hormone therapy. This percentage is getting bigger during the pandemic, where the majority of respondents, namely 81% stated that they do not take hormone therapy.

Graphic 36. Hormone Therapy Practice Before and During the COVID-19

■ Use Hormone Therapy
■ Do Not Use Hormone Therapy

Graphic 35. Comparison of Hormone Therapy by Gender Identity

When observed based on gender identity groups, both transwomen and transmen mostly stated that they did not do hormone therapy, both before the pandemic and especially during the COVID-19 pandemic. When further asked to 354 transgender respondents who stated that they did not take hormone therapy during the pandemic, the majority (73%) stated that they had indeed decided not to do so because of awareness of risks and awareness of acceptance of the body. The reason for limited funds was stated by 20% of respondents. As income decreases (see discussion on the impact on economic conditions), it is automatically realized to prioritize the use of money for basic needs (food and shelter).

Table 5. Main Reason Not To Do Hormone Therapy

Reason	No of Respondents	Percent	Valid Percent
Have no money to buy	70	16%	20%
Do not dare to leave the house/are afraid of catching the virus	11	3%	3%
Never do hormone therapy	259	59%	73%
Have quitted hormone therapy	8	2%	2%
Access is hampered due to COVID-19 pandemic	5	1%	1%
Other	1	0%	0%
Total	354	81%	100%
Missing System	84	19%	
Total	438	100%	

Regarding feelings or psychological conditions during the COVID-19 pandemic, more than half of respondents (59%) said they felt uncomfortable (43% said they were uncomfortable and 16% said they were very uncomfortable). About a third of respondents (34%) stated that they were still able to respond to the pandemic with a fairly stable (normal) psychological condition. Thus, it can be seen that there is a tendency for the COVID-19 pandemic condition to have the potential to have an impact on transgender groups in Indonesia.

Graphic 36. Psychic Conditions During the COVID-19 Pandemic

Mental health services are found to be far beyond the reach of transgender groups in Indonesia. When asked to respondents who specifically stated that they felt uncomfortable during the COVID-19 pandemic, almost all respondents (98%) stated that they did not access mental health services. When asked what were the reasons for not accessing mental health services, at least a third (34%) stated that the high cost of mental health services was still the main obstacle.

In addition, there are still 19% of other respondents who stated that they still have their own concerns about meeting with psychiatrists and psychological counselors. The lingering impact of getting a stigma, especially as a group that deviates from the general public, and is even considered as a person with mental disorders, is definitely a barrier for transgender people to want to access mental health services. Apart from still feeling worried or unprepared, at least 11% of respondents stated that they did not have an understanding of mental health services. About 25% of respondents who stated that they did not access mental health services still considered that they had not seen the need to access mental health services. Out of the group of respondents who stated that they did not need to access mental health services, around 17% stated that they prefer to solve problems related to their own psychological conditions by themselves, while 8% stated that they did not need mental health services.

Graphic 37. Access Preference to Mental Health Services

Graphic 38. Main Reasons for Not Accessing Mental Health Services

During the COVID-19 pandemic, it becomes inevitably more time will be spent at home or in other places of residence. Boredom, the pressure of uncertainty or other factors certainly make transgender people uncomfortable. Moreover, it is generally known that transgender people live far from their biological families because of rejection or simply not being able to withstand all forms of encountered pressure. Fortunately, during this pandemic, most respondents (90%) stated that they had a support system.

Graphic 39. Support System Availability

When asked who was the support system, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, most respondents (85%) stated that they considered friends or collectives among other transgender/LGBTI people as the closest support system. Then, even though many are far from their families, almost half of the respondents mentioned family as part of their support system. Relationship partner are third stated as part of the support system. It is interesting to observe that neighbors or non-LGBTI friends - especially those who live close together - can also be a support system for transgender groups during the COVID-19 pandemic. About 18% of respondents claimed this.

Graphic 40. Support System During the COVID-19 Pandemic

When compared between the two age groups, namely transgender young and adults, there is no difference regarding the support system. The two groups show the same pattern. Most of the daily support comes from friends or collectives among transgender/LGBTI people. With still not being able to access mental health services, the existence of a support system during a pandemic, especially with people living in their neighborhood, this becomes one of the important factors in strengthening transgender groups in facing situations marked by uncertainty and health threats. Next support systems mentioned are family and spouses, then neighbors or friends from non-LGBTI groups.

Graphic 41. Support System per Age Group

When asked about whether or not they consumed ARVs (Anti Retrovirals), each respondent was given the opportunity to refuse to answer (especially since the question whether they took ARV before the pandemic). In the analysis process, respondents who are not willing to answer are treated as missing value so they are not included in the calculation process. From a total of 438 respondents, 18 respondents stated that they were not willing to answer (4%). Of the 420 respondents who were willing to answer, the majority (86%) stated that they did not take ARVs before the pandemic. Only about 14% of respondents stated that they had consumed ARVs since before the COVID-19 pandemic.

Graphic 42. Consumption of ARVs Before the COVID-19 Pandemic

Graphic 43. Consumption of ARVs During COVID-19

For the next process, data from 14% of these respondents or a number of 57 people were asked again whether during the pandemic they were still taking ARVs. Almost all of these respondents (96%) stated that they were still taking ARVs. Only two people (4%) stated that they did not take ARVs during the COVID-19 pandemic. Both respondents are transwomen. One of the transwomen stated that she no longer consumed because she had kidney stones. Meanwhile, the other transwoman did not consume it because she was affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, where she had difficulty arranging a doctor's referral letter from her domicile to access ARVs when forced to be in another area during the pandemic.

Table 6. Consumption of ARVs Before and During the COVID-19 Pandemic per Gender Identity

Gender Identity	Number & Percentage	Before the COVID-19 Pandemic			During the COVID-19 Pandemic		
		Consume	Do not consume	Total	Consume	Do not consume	Total
Transwomen	Number	56	252	308	54	2	56
	%	18%	82%	100%	96%	4%	100%
Transmen	Number	1	111	112	1	0	1
	%	1%	99%	100%	100%	0%	100%
Total	Number	57	363	420	55	2	57
	%	13.6%	86.4%	100.0%	96%	4%	100%

04

CONCLUSION AND
RECOMMENDATION

CONCLUSION

1

From the economic aspect, a drastic decrease in income (up to 58% in nominal rupiahs), where the majority of 70% who claimed to still have a steady source of income (before the pandemic 95%), at the time of the COVID-19 pandemic had income below two million rupiah per month. Before the COVID-19 pandemic alone, it could not be said that transgender people in Indonesia already had sufficient income, because mostly (69%) had a maximum income of five million rupiahs per month. Certainly, restricting activities outside the home has a big impact on the constraints for transgender groups to work. This constraint mainly affects the transwoman group, who generally rely on jobs in fields that require direct and close physical contact with customers (working in salons/spas/reflection and as sex workers). In fact, it was admitted that some transwoman respondents, in order to earn an income, they tried to earn income as sex workers or offered mobile salon/make-up/massage services. This further adds to the vulnerability, especially among the transwoman group, to be infected with COVID-19 and even become a group that has the potential to transmit (carrier). Meanwhile, for the transman group, although generally they did not rely too much on fields such as the transwoman group, there was a decrease in wages and the closure of workplaces. To survive the COVID-19 pandemic, most respondents rely on assistance/loans from their families and also use existing savings/money deposits. In the end, the majority of respondents estimated that they would only last for three months during the COVID-19 pandemic.

2

From the aspect of independence, more than half of transgender groups in Indonesia (71%) have received support from other parties during the COVID-19 pandemic. Although 71% of transgender groups had received assistance during the COVID-19 pandemic, there is a very significant difference between transwomen and transmen. 81% of the transwoman group had received support, this figure is quite high compared to the transman group, where less than half (44%) had received support. This condition occurs because the majority of the transwoman group work as sex workers and salons, which in fact during the COVID-19 pandemic they could not work and earn income. As much as 80% of aid received comes from fellow communities, especially NGOs, LGBT collectives, religious institutions. Meanwhile, the government only contributed 27% in providing support to transgender people during COVID-19. Whereas in terms of providing support, transgender groups experience rejection because of the stigma and censure of their gender identity as transgender (21%) because of this stigma then they are not a priority for support (19%) apart from not being a priority, a fairly common reason is because they do not have identity card (12%).

3

The impact on security shows that during the COVID-19 pandemic, cases involving security forces were the highest at 36%. These cases of violence consisted of threats by the authorities (31%) and being arrested by the security forces (5%). When digging deeper, several reasons for these threats and arrests were made because some transgender groups left their homes to continue working during the COVID-19 pandemic. The decision to leave the house during the pandemic to keep working is an option that many transgender groups must continue to make because the government does not provide them with basic necessities. As many as 21% of transgender groups did not report cases of violence because they felt fear. The fear that often occurs is the existence of stigma and acts of victimization by the police when they want to report cases. This fear is also closely related to other data, namely that the perpetrators of violence are security forces (4%) so that transgender groups feel that there is no benefit (2%) and will add new violence from the apparatus. Another reason is that 14% of transgender people think that the violence they experience is tolerable. This attitude is a form of normalization of violence experienced by transgender groups who think that they deserve violence because of their gender identity. This normalization of violence is understood both personally and collectively. Because of this attitude, transgender people do not feel the need to increase the problem (18%). Many transgender groups feel that reporting a case of violence that they have experienced will increase or increase the problem. Regarding the status of feeling safe, there was an increase of 1.733% related to the insecurity felt by transgender people in Indonesia.

4

When looking at the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the health sector, one thing that is relieving is that there is a good awareness of the body image and also self-acceptance. This is proof of one of the successes of the SOGIESC (Sexual Orientation, Gender Identity and Expression, Sexual Characteristic) education conducted by various LGBTI institutions. Both before and during the COVID-19 pandemic, the majority of transgender respondents stated that they did not take hormone therapy. Then for access to ARVs it also seems that there are no difficulties. The majority of respondents who had consumed ARV since before the pandemic stated that they could still access ARVs. What is worrying is that there are still far away mental health services for transgender groups. Financial limitations, lack of understanding of mental services, and fear of stigma and discrimination when accessing are still the three main obstacles for transgender people in Indonesia in accessing mental health services.

RECOMMENDATION

1

Regarding the impact on the economy, there are at least two types of recommendations submitted based on the time period (short and long). In the short term, with the drastic decline in income among transgender people, it is inevitable that cash transfers will become a priority. In addition, serious efforts are needed regarding the dissemination of information on COVID-19. There are still many (especially in the transwoman group) who rely on their source of income at work, with direct physical contact with other people, a problem that must be resolved. Besides the risk of contracting and spreading COVID-19, it must also be acknowledged that professions such as sex workers, salons or massage have the potential to be infected or transmit viruses or other types of microbes that can cause other diseases. Thus, in the long term it is necessary to design initiatives that can provide a broader range of skills or expertise for transgender groups. For this aspect, further studies are needed to map the potential and interests of transgender groups in Indonesia. In fact, advocating for access to education and formal employment is inevitably a priority in designing long-term program directions for transgender groups in Indonesia.

2

In an effort to ensure the independence of transgender groups in Indonesia in a pandemic situation, two recommendations were made. First, the Indonesian Transgender Coalition needs to encourage and ensure the Indonesian government through advocacy to increase their role and function in providing basic needs assistance to transgender groups in Indonesia. Because if you only expect assistance from NGOs or fellow transgender or LGBTI collectives, the community is guaranteed to have limitations and capacities. Because the pandemic has an impact on all Indonesian people. Therefore, the government must be encouraged to play an active role in providing equal, fair and non-discriminatory assistance. Second, the Indonesian Transgender Coalition (JTID) needs to start thinking about developing projects with the intention of strengthening the sustainable economy for transgender groups in Indonesia, so that they are prepared to face crises in the long term. This is expected to improve the welfare of transgender groups in Indonesia.

3

In ensuring access to justice and security for transgender groups, it is necessary to have holistic advocacy action including recording and documenting cases, assisting cases, advocating for policies and recovering victims. This is very urgent to do because the prolonged pandemic crisis will add to the number of violence against transgender groups in Indonesia. In an effort to increase the resilience of transgender groups, especially in dealing with and resolving cases of violence they experience, it is necessary to design initiatives to strengthen the capacity of paralegals, advocacy, trauma healing, holistic security and human rights. In this case JTID can design the initiative independently or collaborate with support system institutions (allies) who are experts in carrying out capacity building related to the above.

4

In the health sector, with the good awareness of transgender groups in Indonesia about body images, SOGIESC capacity strengthening activities can be an entry point for increasing knowledge and understanding of other issues, including the issue of COVID-19 which is specifically designed for transgender groups and other LGBTI groups. It could also be considered to develop guidelines for hormonal therapy in transgender groups as part of the SOGIESC material. Access to ARV for transgender PLWHA (people living with HIV AIDS) was still good at least until this survey was conducted. However, to ensure that there is a steady supply of ARVs for transgender groups, initiatives need to be designed with health agencies and institutions or programs working on the issue of HIV AIDS. Finally, regarding mental health, this issue needs to be included as part of the SOGIESC material. To fight the pathologization or psychopathologization of transgender groups and other LGBTI groups, increasing understanding among transgender people about gender identity and expression and sexuality is not a mental disorder that needs to be improved. Then, considering that it is still difficult for transgender groups to access health insurance that finances mental health services (BPJS) and considering the high costs of accessing mental health services, it is necessary to prioritize initiatives aimed at strengthening the capacity of transgender people in facing various pressures (especially the impact of the pandemic COVID-19). In addition, identification and approach to psychiatric experts, psychological counsellors and other mental health services also need to be carried out immediately, especially considering the trend of the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on economic conditions which has an impact on security conditions and the independence of transgender groups in Indonesia.

**RESEARCHERS
PROFILE**

NOVA CHRISTINA

HER five years of experience, from 2001 to 2006 as a researcher at Kompas Media Nusantara as a social survey team, has become a significant asset in his career as a researcher. During her time at Kompas, she was provided a lot of opportunities to be able to conduct social and business research both qualitatively and quantitatively. She has a passion for research and always identifies himself as a researcher. Apart from being a researcher, she then increased her capacity to work on social issues by joining non-governmental organizations both international and national scale organizations.

After completing her postgraduate studies at Leiden University, the Netherlands, she decided to explore her expertise in the humanitarian field, joining as a Monitoring and Evaluation Specialist at Save the Children for the Aceh Tsunami Response Program.

Following the end of the Aceh Tsunami Response Program, she briefly joined as the National Monitoring and Reporting Coordinator at World Vision Indonesia in 2010. In addition, she then tried to further explore his capacity to become an independent evaluator and researcher. She is able to design research methods with both quantitative and qualitative approaches and has been trusted by institutions such as CARITAS - Switzerland, Australia Aid (before becoming DFAT) and even World Vision Indonesia to lead evaluation activities.

Her spare time as a freelance worker is utilized properly to continue to increase her capacity and knowledge in various fields through workshops or

courses. So, do not be surprised if she also has good knowledge in the fields of Human Rights, Gender, SOGIESC, as well as in the environmental field.

She consistently continues her career as an expert in the field of research and monitoring and evaluation. Major institutions in Indonesia such as the Partnership, Mercy Corps Indonesia, the Australia-Indonesia Electoral Support Program (AIESP), to the Legal Aid for Village Program (Australia Indonesia Partnership for Justice / Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade of Australia), have felt their expertise. She was even trusted by the US Department of States as a Senior Qualitative Researcher to be involved in gender-based research activities.

She currently works as a program advisor/consultant for the SOGIESC-based institute, Arus Pelangi. She has been able to increase the capacity of key staff from 12 member institutions of the Arus Pelangi Federation regarding program management. Her seriousness and commitment to apply human values as well as her love of sharing knowledge and experience have enabled SOGIESC-based institutions from 8 provinces to start improving program governance in their respective institutions.

She also started the establishment of E/Quality as an institution that has a vision to provide enlightenment and increase capacity by promoting human values and equality. It encourages the involvement of anyone who is called to develop themselves and share to join E/Quality

EDISON BUTARBUTAR

Edison is known to be quite active in various organizations since he became a student at the University of North Sumatra; especially organizations related to their field of study, anthropology. Starting from the research coordinator at the Study Group of culture, to being the general secretary of the Indonesian Anthropological Kinship Network.

When he finished his studies in 2014, he was still active in various organizations in North Sumatra. As chairman and founder of Cangkang Queer and Project Officer at the United North Sumatra Alliance, until finally he set foot in Jakarta to expand his capacity and experience in the field of management and organizational governance programs by serving as Program Manager at the Arus Pelangi Federation and currently serving as Program Manager Crisis Response Mechanism (CRM) Consortium.

His activities in the organization have shaped his personal character as a person capable of leadership. Meanwhile, the knowledge he has gained from organizing and from the various trainings he has participated in has also shaped his character as a Human Rights Defender. The

combination of on-campus and off-campus knowledge is often expressed in various publications in the form of books or research.

Ethnography of Sexuality in the City of Medan (2014), Report on the Situation of LGBTI in North Sumatra (2015), The Silent Way of Ancestral Religion (2016) and Farel, The Long Road to Justice for a Transgender (2019), Analysis of the Situation of Transgender in Indonesia (2020), etc., are examples of his various thoughts and research results juxtaposed with various experiences in the field as a human rights defender.

In the field of Sexual Orientation and Gender Identity Expression and Sexual Characteristic (SOGIESC), Edison is perhaps one of the few young people and LGBTI who has mastered the knowledge of SOGIESC. In the midst of situations and conditions in Indonesia that are discriminatory against LGBTIQ people, his knowledge and experience will certainly be very useful in the long aim of human rights defenders to eliminate discrimination against LGBTIQ people.

b

ATTACHMENT

Kuesioner Dampak Pandemi Covid-19 Terhadap Komunitas Transgender di Indonesia

Informed Consent:

Selamat pagi/siang/malam, saya _____, saat ini sedang membantu Jaringan Transgender Indonesia (JTID) untuk melakukan kajian terkait Dampak Pandemi Covid-19 Terhadap Komunitas Transgender di Indonesia. Saya akan melakukan wawancara singkat dengan Anda. Adapun informasi terkait identitas Anda kami jamin kerahasiaannya dan tidak akan disebarluaskan ke pihak lain tanpa seizin Anda. Wawancara akan berlangsung sekitar setengah jam.

No	Pertanyaan	Jawaban	Keterangan
00	Apakah Anda bersedia untuk diwawancara?	1. Bersedia 2. Tidak bersedia	Jika tidak bersedia, akhiri proses wawancara, ganti responden
01	Nama enumerator/pewawancara		

Profil Responden:

No	Pertanyaan	Jawaban	Keterangan
R01	Nama responden (tuliskan, tidak harus nama sesuai KTP)		
R02	Identitas gender	1. Transpuan/waria 2. Transman/priawan	
R03	Kota/Kabupaten		
R04	Propinsi	1. DKI Jakarta 2. Jawa Barat 3. Jawa Timur 4. Sumatra Utara 5. Kalimantan Selatan 6. Bali 7. Sulawesi Selatan 8. Kalimantan Tengah 9. Papua 10. Papua Barat 11. Maluku	
R05	Usia	Tahun	
R06	Nomor handphone/telepon yang aktif		
R07	Pendidikan Terakhir	1. Tidak sekolah 2. SD/setaraf 3. SMP/setaraf 4. SMA/setaraf 5. Diploma 6. Sarjana (S1) 7. Pasca Sarjana	

Akses terhadap Informasi Covid-19

No	Pertanyaan	Jawaban	Keterangan
C01	Seberapa sering Anda mengikuti perkembangan Covid-19?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Tidak pernah sama sekali 2. Hanya sesekali saja (jika ingat atau ada perkembangan kasus tertentu) 3. Sekali dalam seminggu 4. Hampir setiap hari 5. Setiap hari 	Jika 1 (tidak pernah), loncat ke E01
C02	Dari mana sumber informasi terkait perkembangan covid-19 selama ini? (Jawaban bisa lebih dari satu)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Pemberitaan/media online 2. Pemberitaan di televisi 3. Grup chat (WA/LINE/SIGNAL/dll) 4. Sosial media (FB, IG, Twitter, dll) 5. Koran/majalah cetak 6. Selebaran 7. Spanduk/iklan di jalanan 8. Sosialisasi pemerintah 9. Lainnya: 	

Dampak terhadap Pendapatan

No	Pertanyaan	Jawaban	Keterangan
E01	Sebelum pandemi Covid-19, apakah Anda memiliki/tidak memiliki sumber penghasilan tetap?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ya/memiliki 2. Tidak/tidak memiliki 	Jika 2 (tidak/tidak memiliki), loncat ke E03
E02	Dari mana sumber penghasilan Anda sebelum Covid-19? (jawaban dapat lebih dari satu)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Bekerja di perusahaan 2. Pegawai negeri 3. Bekerja di LSM 4. Bekerja di NGO 5. Bekerja di toko 6. Berdagang 7. Gojek/grab 8. Jasa online/aplikasi (goclean, golife) 9. Ojek biasa 10. Asisten rumah tangga 11. Bekerja di salon 12. Bekerja di café/karaoke 13. Mengamen di jalan 14. Pekerja seks di jalan 15. Pekerja seks online 16. Lainnya (tuliskan): 	

No	Pertanyaan	Jawaban	Keterangan
E03	Berapa rata-rata pendapatan bulanan Anda sebelum pandemi Covid-19? (dapat dihitung juga dari minimal pengeluaran rutin bulanan)	Rp. _____	
E04	Aset apa saja yang dimiliki sebelum pandemi covid-19? (jawaban bisa lebih dari satu)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Rumah 2. Tanah 3. Ruko 4. Sepeda motor 5. Mobil 6. Emas/perhiasan berharga lainnya 7. Tabungan/simpanan uang 8. Komputer/laptop 9. Smartphone 10. Televisi 11. Tidak memiliki 12. Lainnya (tuliskan): 	
E05	Saat ini (saat pandemi covid-19), apakah Anda memiliki/tidak memiliki sumber penghasilan tetap?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ya/memiliki 2. Tidak/tidak memiliki 	Jika 2, loncat ke E07
E06	Dari mana sumber penghasilan Anda saat Covid-19? (jawaban dapat lebih dari satu)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Bekerja di perusahaan 2. Pegawai negeri 3. Bekerja di LSM 4. Bekerja di NGO 5. Bekerja di toko 6. Berdagang 7. Gojek/grab 8. Jasa online/aplikasi (goclean, golife) 9. Ojek biasa 10. Asisten rumah tangga 11. Bekerja di salon 12. Bekerja di café/karaoke 13. Mengamen di jalan 14. Pekerja seks di jalan 15. Pekerja seks online 16. Lainnya (tuliskan): 	
E07	Berapa rata-rata pendapatan bulanan Anda saat pandemi Covid-19? (dapat dihitung juga dari minimal pengeluaran rutin bulanan)	Rp. _____	
E08	Aset apa saja yang dimiliki saat pandemi covid-19?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Rumah 2. Tanah 3. Ruko 4. Sepeda motor 5. Mobil 	

No	Pertanyaan	Jawaban	Keterangan
		6. Emas/perhiasan berharga lainnya 7. Tabungan/simpanan uang 8. Komputer/laptop 9. Smartphone 10. Televisi 11. Tidak memiliki 12. Lainnya:	
E09	Apakah pendapatan Anda saat ini dapat mencukupi kebutuhan pangan/makanan Anda?	1. Ya/cukup 2. Tidak/tidak cukup	
E10	Apakah pendapatan Anda saat ini dapat mencukupi kebutuhan untuk tempat tinggal Anda? (sewa atau angsuran tempat tinggal)	1. Ya/cukup 2. Tidak/tidak cukup	
E11	Apakah pendapatan Anda saat ini dapat mencukupi kebutuhan untuk listrik Anda?	1. Ya/cukup 2. Tidak/tidak cukup	
E12	Apakah pendapatan Anda saat ini dapat mencukupi kebutuhan air bersih?	1. Ya/cukup 2. Tidak/tidak cukup	
E13	Apakah pendapatan Anda saat ini dapat mencukupi untuk kebutuhan pengobatan jika sakit?	1. Ya/cukup 2. Tidak/tidak cukup	
E14	Apakah pendapatan Anda saat ini dapat mencukupi untuk kebutuhan komunikasi?	1. Ya/cukup 2. Tidak/tidak cukup	
E15	Apakah ada upaya lain yang Anda lakukan untuk bertahan selama pandemi Covid-19?	1. Ya/ada 2. Tidak/Tidak ada	Jika 2 (Tidak/tidak ada) loncat ke E17
E16	Jika ada, upaya apa yang Anda lakukan untuk bertahan selama pandemi Covid-19? (jawaban bisa lebih dari satu)	1. Menggadaikan aset yang dimiliki 2. Menjual aset yang dimiliki 3. Menggunakan tabungan 4. Mencari bantuan/pinjaman dari orang tua 5. Mencari bantuan/pinjaman dari teman 6. Mencari bantuan/pinjaman dari orang/pihak lain 7. Lainnya (tuliskan):	

No	Pertanyaan	Jawaban	Keterangan
E17	Apakah Anda memiliki tanggungan ekonomi (keluarga atau kerabat)?	1. Ya/memiliki 2. Tidak/tidak memiliki	Jika 2 (tidak/tidak memiliki), loncat ke E19
E18	Jika ada/memiliki, berapa orang yang tergantung/ditanggung dari pendapatan Anda? (orang yang ditanggung adalah orang yang hidupnya bergantung pada penghasilan responden)	_____ orang	
E19	Dengan memperhitungkan sumber daya yang ada saat ini, jika harus tetap berada di rumah, menurut Anda berapa lama sumber daya yang ada dapat menunjang kebutuhan Anda? (tuliskan jawaban)	_____ bulan 111. Kurang dari sebulan	

Dampak terhadap Kemandirian

No	Pertanyaan	Jawaban	Keterangan
M01	Di mana tempat tinggal Anda selama ini? (setidaknya selama 6 bulan terakhir sebelum pandemi covid-19)	1. Di rumah sendiri 2. Di rumah sewa sendiri 3. Di kamar kos/sewa kamar 4. Di rumah keluarga 5. Di rumah kerabat 6. Di tempat/rumah teman 7. Tidak ada tempat tinggal tetap/berpindah-pindah 8. Lainnya (tuliskan):	Jika 4 (di rumah keluarga) dan 5 (di rumah kerabat), loncat ke M03
M02	Saat pandemi Covid-19 ini, apakah Anda memiliki/tidak memiliki rencana untuk pulang kampung atau kembali ke rumah keluarga?	1. Ya/memiliki 2. Tidak/tidak memiliki	
M03	Apakah Anda pernah/tidak pernah menerima bantuan dari pihak lain selama pandemi covid-19 ini?	1. Ya/pernah 2. Tidak/tidak pernah	Jika 2 (tidak/tidak pernah), loncat ke
M04	Jika ya/pernah menerima bantuan, apa bentuk bantuan yang pernah diterima? (jawaban boleh lebih dari satu)	1. Sembako 2. Dana tunai 3. Lainnya (tuliskan):	
M05	Dari mana bantuan diterima? (jawaban boleh lebih dari satu)	1. Orang tidak dikenal 2. Lembaga agama	

No	Pertanyaan	Jawaban	Keterangan
		3. LSM/NGO 4. Pemerintah 5. Lainnya (tuliskan):	
M06	Pernah/tidak pernah Anda mengalami kesulitan dalam mengakses bantuan?	1. Ya/Pernah 2. Tidak/Tidak pernah	Jika 2 (tidak/tidak pernah), loncat ke S01
M07	Jika pernah, menurut Anda apa yang paling menyebabkan Anda sulit mengakses bantuan?	1. Penolakan karena identitas/ekspresi gender/stigma/sentimen pada kelompok LGBTI 2. Jumlah bantuan terbatas 3. Tidak memiliki KTP 4. Tidak prioritas 5. Lainnya (tuliskan):	

Dampak terhadap Keamanan

No	Pertanyaan	Jawaban	Keterangan
S01	Sebelum pandemi covid-19, sering/tidak sering Anda beraktivitas di luar rumah?	1. Sangat sering 2. Sering 3. Cukup sering 4. Jarang 5. Tidak pernah	
S02	Saat pandemi covid-19, sering/tidak sering Anda beraktivitas di luar rumah?	1. Sangat sering 2. Sering 3. Cukup sering 4. Jarang 5. Tidak pernah	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jika jawaban 1, 2 dan 3, ke no S03 • Jika jawaban 4 dan 5, loncat ke no S04
S03	Saat pandemi covid-19, apa alasan utama Anda (cukup) sering beraktivitas di luar rumah?	1. Untuk mencari penghasilan/bekerja 2. Ke rumah sakit/karena sakit 3. Lainnya (tuliskan):	Langsung ke S05
S04	Saat pandemi covid-19, apa alasan utama Anda jarang/tidak pernah beraktivitas di luar rumah?	1. Mengikuti himbuan pemerintah/takut tertular covid-19 2. Tidak bisa bekerja/tempat bekerja tutup 3. Lainnya (tuliskan):	

No	Pertanyaan	Jawaban	Keterangan
S05	Saat pandemi covid-19, pernah/tidak pernah Anda mengakses layanan kesehatan?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ya/pehah 2. Tidak/tidak pernah 	Jika 2 (tidak/tidak pernah), loncat ke S08
S06	Jika pernah, pernah/tidak pernah Anda mengalami perlakuan yang diskriminatif/tidak nyaman?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ya/pehah 2. Tidak/tidak pernah 	Jika 2 (tidak/tidak pernah), loncat ke S08
S07	Jika pernah, perlakukan diskriminatif/tidak nyaman seperti apa yang dialami? (jawaban bisa lebih dari satu)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Tidak dilayani 2. Dibedakan dengan pasien lain 3. Dipanggil sesuai nama KTP 4. Lainnya (tuliskan): 	
S08	Saat pandemi covid-19, pernah/tidak pernah Anda mengalami gangguan/insiden keamanan?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ya/pehah 2. Tidak/tidak pernah 	Jika 2 (tidak/tidak pernah), loncat ke S12
S09	Jika pernah, insiden keamanan seperti apa yang Anda alami? (jawaban bisa lebih dari satu)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Diancam warga 2. Diancam aparat keamanan 3. Diancam preman 4. Diusir dari tempat tinggal 5. Ditangkap aparat keamanan/ketertiban 6. Lainnya (tuliskan): 	
S10	Apakah anda melaporkan/tidak melaporkan insiden yang anda alami ke pihak aparat keamanan?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ya/melaporkan 2. Tidak/tidak melaporkan 	Jika 1 (ya/melaporkan), loncat ke S12
S11	Jika tidak melaporkan insiden keamanan, apa alasan utama Anda tidak melapor?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Takut 2. Pelaku kekerasan adalah aparat keamanan 3. Tidak paham cara melaporkan 4. Lainnya (tuliskan): 	
S12	Sebelum pandemi covid-19, bagaimana Anda menilai rasa aman?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sangat aman 2. Aman 3. Cukup aman 4. Tidak aman 5. Sangat tidak aman 	
S13	Saat pandemi covid-19, bagaimana Anda menilai rasa aman?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sangat aman 2. Aman 3. Cukup aman 4. Tidak aman 5. Sangat tidak aman 	

Dampak Terhadap Kesehatan

No	Pertanyaan	Jawaban	Keterangan
K01	Sebelum pandemi covid-19, apakah anda melakukan/tidak melakukan terapi hormon?	1. Ya 2. Tidak	Jika 2 (tidak), Loncat ke K04
K02	Saat pandemic covid-19 apakah anda melakukan/tidak melakukan terapi hormon?	1. Ya 2. Tidak	Jika 1 (ya), loncat ke K04
K03	Apa alasan utama Anda tidak lagi mengkonsumsi hormon saat pandemi covid-19?	1. Tidak memiliki uang untuk membeli 2. Tidak berani keluar rumah/takut tertular virus 3. Toko/tempat penjualan tutup 4. Memang tidak terapi hormon 5. Lainnya:	
K04	Bagaimana perasaan atau kondisi psikis Anda selama pandemic covid-19?	1. Sangat baik/Sangat nyaman 2. Baik/nyaman 3. Biasa saja 4. Tidak baik/Tidak nyaman 5. Sangat tidak baik/Sangat tidak nyaman	Jika jawaban 1, 2 lanjut ke K07 Jika jawaban 3, 4, 5 loncat ke K05
K05	Jika tidak baik, apakah Anda mengakses/tidak mengakses layanan kesehatan mental untuk mengatasinya?	1. Ya/mengakses 2. Tidak/tidak mengakses	Jika 1, loncat ke K07
K06	Apa alasan utama Anda tidak mengakses layanan kesehatan mental?	1. Tidak memiliki uang 2. Tidak berani keluar rumah 3. Belum siap secara mental/tidak berani bertemu psikiater/psikolog 4. Lainnya:	
K07	Apakah Anda memiliki/tidak memiliki sistem pendukung untuk bercerita dan	1. Ya/memiliki 2. Tidak/tidak memiliki	Jika 2, ke K09

No	Pertanyaan	Jawaban	Keterangan
	berbagi terkait situasi yang Anda rasakan selama covid-19?		
K08	Jika memiliki, siapa sistem pendukung pendukung anda tersebut? (jawaban bisa lebih dari satu)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Teman atau kolektif sesama transgender/LGBTI 2. Keluarga 3. Pasangan/pacar 4. Lainnya: 	
K09	Apakah sebelum covid-19 anda mengkonsumsi/tidak mengkonsumsi ARV?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ya/mengkonsumsi 2. Tidak/tidak mengkonsumsi 3. Tidak bersedia menjawab 	Jika 2, loncat ke D01
K10	Apakah saat covid-19 anda mengkonsumsi/tidak mengkonsumsi ARV?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ya/mengkonsumsi 2. Tidak/tidak mengkonsumsi 	Jika 1, loncat ke D01
K11	Jika tidak mengkonsumsi, apa alasan utama Anda tidak mengkonsumsi ARV selama covid-19?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Tidak memiliki uang untuk mengambil/akses ke Puskesmas/rumah sakit 2. Stok ARV kosong 3. Tidak berani keluar rumah untuk mengambil ke layananan 4. Lainnya: 	

Penutup

Penghargaan untuk responden:

Terima kasih untuk kesedian waktu. Pada pengumpulan data ini, pihak JTID memberikan kompensasi sejumlah Rp 150,000 kepada setiap responden yang diwawancarai. Untuk informasi lebih lanjut dapat menghubungi Rebecca Nyuei 081290317897

No	Pertanyaan	Jawaban	Keterangan
D01	Apakah Anda bersedia/tidak bersedia untuk menerima kompensasi?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Bersedia 2. Tidak bersedia 	

-wawancara selesai-

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